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MSc Dissertation

**PEOPLE'S ATTITUDES AND ACTIONS OF PRIVACY ON
SOCIAL MEDIA: DOES THE GREAT FIREWALL MATTER?**

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Abstract

Current studies are missing some points when researching about digital privacy, they either ignore the importance of social media or only limit to several western social media platforms. There are two aims of this dissertation to fill these gaps, to broadly generalise people's attitudes and actions of privacy on social media and compare the difference between non-Chinese and Chinese social media users. Through the interview, the findings show that people are very concerned about privacy on social media, and they have some strategies to protect it. What they care about the most is the visibility of their social media contents, and they would like to control who the audience is. Non-Chinese and Chinese share the similar attitudes of privacy, however, Chinese users have different protective actions because of the characters of social media they are using. Finally, this dissertation rises a different form of privacy paradox that despite the awareness of privacy risks, people have less understood of data collecting by organisations, and tend to have no actions to protect it.

Keywords

Privacy, Digital Privacy, Privacy Paradox, Social Media, Big Data, The Great Firewall

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1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background

What is “Privacy”? It can be understated as to how people control their personal information (Westin, 1968; Allen, 1988). Because of the development of “Web 2.0” and “Big data”, nowadays, “Digital” and “Data” have become an important part when discussing privacy, and this trend can be seen from recent research directions. Under this trend, issues of digital privacy start being concerned when it comes to the Internet, furthermore, scholars are questioning the existing of anonymity in the information era (Haggerty and Ericson, 2000; Prabhakar, Pankanti and Jain, 2003; Ohm, 2010). Another area that attracts scholars’ attention is the phenomenon of privacy paradox, which indicates the conflict between people’s attitudes and actions of privacy (Norberg, Horne and Horne, 2007; Barth and de Jong, 2017; Gerber, Gerber and Volkamer, 2018).

1.2 Research Question

In previous studies about privacy, there are two gaps can be identified. First is that the e-commerce area has been studied too much, and consider human’s activities online nowadays, data on social media occupy the most proportion of the Internet world (Salim, 2019). Therefore, it should be the most-focused field about digital privacy. Second is that when it comes to the current researches about privacy on social media, they often only focus on a specific platform, or exclude the big social media world behind China’s Great Firewall. To fill these gaps, two aims of this dissertation are brought out: to find out people’s attitudes and actions of privacy on social media and explore the difference of these on both sides on the Great Firewall.

1.3 Research Method

A face-to-face semi-structured interview is used to do the research. Questionnaire of the interview is developed from Buchanan et al. (2007) and Black, Setterfield and Warren (2018)’s research. Participants are carefully chosen. They are in a specific age group (18 to 34), which is the age that uses social media the most (Mander and Kavanagh, 2019). Nationality of the participants is manipulated too in order to achieve the second aim of this dissertation to see the Great Firewall’s effect. Half of them are from China and others are not. Finally, thematic analysis is applied to analyse the results of the interview, and there are ten themes can be identified.

2 Literature Review

2.1 From “Privacy” to “Digital Privacy”

2.1.1 Development of “Privacy”

Traditionally, when western scholars are discussing what is “Privacy”, they are mainly talking about the field that separated from the “Public”. This can be indicated from *The Right to Privacy* (Warren and Brandeis, 1890), which has the biggest effect on defining what is “Privacy”. In Warren and Brandeis’ work, although it did not give the whole definition of “Privacy”, it used the phrase “right to be let alone” to explain to the notion of “Privacy”. The usage of “alone” indicates a field that is not in “Public”. Nevertheless, Warren and Brandeis’ work is not the absolute starting point of privacy research, there have been some scholars begins to concern about privacy issue before them. For example, seven years before Warren and Brandeis’ paper, *Liberty, Equality, Fraternity* (Stephen, 1873) briefly discusses privacy. Schoeman (1984) generalises Stephen’s points of privacy that it is about the aspect of secret in people’s lives, and it is not shown to the “Public”. Therefore, despite the huge influence, it can be considered that Warren and Brandeis’ work is a continuation from previous scholars such as Stephen.

After Warren and Brandeis, besides the factor “alone”, scholars extended the notion of “privacy”. From *The Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (Roosevelt et al., 1948), which brought out by the United Nation, it can be seen that “Privacy” has become to be considered as an element of human rights, and it is not only limited to the right to live privately but also related to the right of non-interference and personal reputation protection. Westin (1968) and Fried (1968) both consider privacy as the right that individuals can decide what kind of information about themselves can be exposed to others. From their interpretations, personal information is brought into the notion of privacy. After, Allen (1988) continues these interpretations and expresses an observation that privacy is a state of an individual's personal information to be inaccessible or not to be shrivelled by others. Gavison (1980) points out when an individual is completely unreachable from others, he can have privacy. From this, he concludes three factors in “Privacy”: Secret, Anonymity and Alone. These three factors are relative to personal information, the attention from others and the physical contact, therefore, Gavison (1980)’s explanation to “Privacy” is more general compared to the scholars before. Inness (1996) brought out another factor “Intimacy” into the notion of “Privacy”. He indicates that privacy shows an individual how to control their level of intimacy with others. The more extent of intimacy between an individual and others, the more personal information that the individual is willing to share with. Moreover, intimacy not only affects the number (quantity) of

information but also the extent of closeness (quality) of information that an individual is willing to share (Inness, 1996).

From this, a rough definition of “Privacy” can be built - it is a state that how people control their personal information. It should be secret and anonymous by individual’s wish, and the extent of secrecy and anonymity of it is decided by the individual's extent of intimacy with others.

2.1.2 Early Research about Privacy

Along with the conceptualising of “Privacy”, people began to recognize that they have the right to privacy. Furthermore, they wanted to know how to protect theirs. Shah (1970) discusses the legal aspect of privacy in the clinical psychological area. Shah organises existing laws about this issue in North America to find out what kinds of boundaries need to be obeyed between psychologists and patients. Ware and Caldwell (1972)’s research focuses on the survey area. Statisticians are bothered by the rate of invalid and refusal answers in the World Fertility Survey, and Ware and Caldwell try to find out the reason behind it. Their result shows that it is because of the sensitivities of some questions. From the participants’ aspect, there are some questions that seem to be too personal for them and violate their privacy. However, from the survey conductor’s aspect, they do not consider these questions to be sensitive. Lewis (1975) studies a different area in the medical field: patients’ drug and alcohol records. In America, in order to track the administrative performance in reducing drug and alcohol problems, public authorities were asking institutions such as a hospital to provide their patients’ information, and it raised issues of patients’ privacy. Lewis (1975) concludes this issue that there may not be the absolute right of privacy in order to maintain the goodness of social order, however, a balance is required between public interests and personal privacy. Kelman (1977) explores privacy issues in the social research area. He indicates that doing social research requires data collecting from humans, and it is a kind of invasion of personal privacy.

From the above, it can be realised that early studies about privacy focus on two directions: patients’ privacy and survey participants’ privacy. Studies about patients’ privacy (Shah, 1970; Lewis, 1975) discuss about how to create a more private way to record patients’ information, to make them share it to the doctor more confidently; studies about survey participants (Ware and Caldwell, 1972; Kelman, 1977) state the potential ethical issues and risks when statistics or researchers collecting people’s response.

2.1.3 Digitalisation of “Privacy”

Before discussing privacy in the Internet field, two basic but important concepts need to be understood, which are “Web 2.0” and “Big Data”. Web 1.0 states an old age that a website is

just controlled by the owner. It cannot interact, and it is not able to respond to the user. Then with the upgrading of technologies, websites can not only store users' input data but also adjust itself to react to the users based on the data they received. This leads to the era of Web 2.0. The key factors of "Web 2.0" are interaction, sharing and relationship (O'Reilly, 2009), and these factors generally become an important part when we talk about the Internet. It can be realised that there is a strong connection between "Web 2.0" and "Big Data". As you can see, the more users interact with websites, the more data would be input, and this causes the emergence of the term "Big Data". The key concept of "Big Data" is simple: a lot of data (Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier, 2013). However, because of the huge amount of data, questions such as how to collect it, how to store it and how to analyse it make it a complicated field (Chen, Mao and Liu, 2014).

Nowadays, there are mainly two types of data usage: commercial usage and governmental usage. For commercial data usage, there are two ways for firms to collect data: from direct interactions and from the third-party providers (CMA, 2015). Literally speaking, direct interactions are customers behaviours such as purchasing a product and requesting query from the firm. During this process, customers are willing to give their information to finish the purchase or get the information, therefore, companies can directly collect these data. Third-party data providers use technology such as cookies to broadly collect customers' Internet activities. Instead of directly applying these data, they sell it to other companies that don't have such collecting technology but still need the data. Two goals for companies to use the data, one is to help them improve their products and services and another is to come out personalised advertisements and suggestions for an individual customer (CMA, 2015). For governmental data usage, other than methods like in the commercial field, there are more ways to collect data. For example, CCTV can be an important data resource. Besides, the speciality of government gives it the ability to access information that is not available to the general organisation (Currie, 2013). There are more reasons for the government to collect data than for merchants, such as fighting crime and public health protection (Kim, Trimi and Chung, 2014). For some countries, surveillance is the main reason to collect data (Currie, 2013).

To sum up, it can be realised that because of the main character of "Web 2.0" and "Big Data", data is mainly provided by users. From users' aspect, it can raise the concern about who could obtain their data, and how the data would be used. Further, users are trying to find a way to protect their data actively. An important phenomenon to indicate this trend is the rise of Adblock. Adblock is a software that not only can block all the ads when surfing the Internet but also prevent users' activities on the Internet to be traced. According to a recent statistic

(Malik, 2019), 47% of internet users globally are using ad-blocker today, and the number is anticipated to grow.

2.1.4 Research about Privacy Nowadays

Before the term “Big Data” is widely used, Solove (2004) has already brought out this phenomenon. He indicates that when people using the internet, their personal information, activities and habits etc. will be collected and kept in databases, and these data will be output and reused to influence our behaviour. He considers it as a big threat of personal privacy because of the uncertain ability of accession by unknown third-party constitutions or individuals and suggests some legal adjustment to reduce this kind of threats. Nissenbaum (2009) concludes that the meaning of digital privacy to people is the action of information sharing an appropriate way, which echoes the notion of privacy which organised from early studies in the previous chapter that privacy is about the control of information. Ohm (2010) makes a strong point that anonymity is a fail in the information age, and the executive and legislative department must act immediately. Boyd and Crawford (2012) talks about the influence of Big Data on culture, technology and scholars, and indicate data privacy as an important ethical issue.

As can be seen, there has been more and more studies in digital privacy since 2000, and several research areas can be identified which are organised below:

Research area: E-Commerce

Privacy about online purchasing is an area that has been researched a lot in the digital privacy field. Miyazaki and Fernandez (2001) explore consumer's perception of online privacy when doing remote purchasing via the Internet. Their result shows that with more internet experience, consumer's concern about security risks would be lower, however, they would care more about online privacy, and it would influence their activities when shopping online. Chellappa and Sin (2005) focus on a specific area: personalising online advertising, which means that after receiving customers' activities on their websites, they promote specific goods to an individual by analysing the received data. Chellappa and Sin (2005)'s study shows that by trust-building campaigns, vendors may be able to collect more customers' information, so it is important for online vendors to realise that the balance of the convenience of service and customers' value such as privacy. Acquisti and Grossklags (2005) research into the influence of privacy concern when online customers are making decisions, and their result shows that people are willing to trade take the risk of privacy violation in order to get some benefits from online vendors such as a discount.

Research area: E-Government

Haggerty and Ericson (2000) discuss the ability of government to monitor people, and point out a conclusion that is similar to Ohm (2010)'s which mentioned earlier in this chapter that anonymity seems to be an impossible thing in this era, 'the disappearance has been disappeared.' Moon (2002) indicates the emergence of E-Government. With the revolution of technologies, more and more government departments are choosing to digitalise the administrative procedures, in order to increase efficiency and reduce paper usage. The privacy issue is a big obstacle in this development because the regulation of data collection, storage and accession have not been completed yet. Prabhakar, Pankanti and Jain (2003) look at the biometric recognition area. Biometric recognition is a technique that uses the unique physiological characteristics of an individual such as fingerprints to identify that person's identity, and more and more governments are using this technology collecting their people's biometric information and build a database in order to fight crime and keep their country safe. Prabhakar, Pankanti and Jain (2003) conclude a statement which is similar to Haggerty and Ericson (2000) and Ohm (2010) that with the rise of this kind of technologies, 'those who desire to remain anonymous in any particular situation could be denied their privacy by biometric recognition.' Nissenbaum (2004) makes a serious statement that the government's surveillance throughout the data collection from digital media is violating people's right to privacy, which causes injustice and can be considered as a tyranny. Dawes (2009) offers a research framework to evaluate governments in digital era, and points out the importance for the government to build trust with their people; Cullen (2009) explores people's interaction of digital information sharing with the government, and suggests that the government needs to consider the culture difference and how they think of privacy when interacting with people.

Research area: Gender, age and cultural differences

Gender, age and cultural differences in people's privacy attitudes and actions have been studied as well. Sheehan (1999) and Garbarino and Strahilevitz (2004) both discuss the gender difference. Sheehan (1999)'s study shows that in attitudes, women are more concerned about the privacy issue when it comes to data collecting within online purchasing, however, for inactions, men are more likely to really do something to protect their data privacy compared to women; Garbarino and Strahilevitz (2004)'s result support Sheehan (1999)'s study that women are really more concerned about privacy lost in attitudes, yet, if some websites or online activities that have potential privacy risks are suggested by friends, women are more willing to take the risk to try the website or do the action compared to men. Livingstone (2008) and Davis and James (2013)'s research are focusing on young people's perspective of privacy. Livingstone (2008) indicates that digital intimacy and identity are important for young people, and in order to maintain and manage their online image, they are

willing to take the risks of privacy exposure. Davis and James (2013), on the other hand, find out that teenagers are protective about their digital privacy. They have several strategies to protect their privacy online and these strategies are more comprehensive and extensive than what adults thought. Crotty et al. (2015) study elders' (over 75 years old) attitudes about information sharing and find that the main factors that affect elders' behaviour about privacy are dignity to maintain their autonomy. Cho, Rivera-Sánchez and Lim (2009) and Miltgen and Peyrat-Guillard (2014) research on the cultural difference and its affection of privacy attitude. Cho, Rivera-Sánchez and Lim (2009) study internet users from five cities: Bengaluru, Seoul, Singapore, Sydney and New York, and the result shows that women in middle age from an individualistic culture care more about digital privacy. Miltgen and Peyrat-Guillard (2014) only focus on Europe countries. They study seven countries in Europe and observe that Europeans from different regions have different reasons behind privacy disclosure.

Research area: Gadgets and techniques

Nowadays, smart gadgets and new techniques contain the ability to record users' data, such as a smartwatch can memorise users' biological and location information. This raises the privacy concerns too scholars are focusing on it now. Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Malhotra (2005) and Dinev and Hart, (2006) provide frameworks to evaluate the quality of digital services, and privacy occupies a big proportion in their frameworks. Weber (2010) presents a different area of privacy concern: The Internet of Things. "Internet of Things" is a technique that uses the Internet to connect and control every object such as door alarms and refrigerators and Weber (2010) points out this is a new area needs to be noticed about personal privacy violation because data collecting is extended from online to offline. Takabi, Joshi and Ahn (2010) focus on another technique: "Cloud Computing". Cloud computing is a service using virtualization to store a huge amount of data more easily, and Takabi, Joshi and Ahn (2010) bring out some solutions to prevent privacy and security issues such as data leaking.

Research area: Privacy paradox

Privacy paradox is a phenomenon emerges in the information age (Norberg, Horne and Horne, 2007; Barth and de Jong, 2017; Gerber, Gerber and Volkamer, 2018). What is privacy paradox? It can be explained through Madden (2014)'s research. In this research, people are very concerned about privacy issues. They do not feel safe to share private information through email and online chatting applications, and they do not believe that the data that they input to commerce or government will be protected enough. However, these concerns do not stop them to use these online services, and they do not adjust or try to reduce the amount of personal information that may be shared online. Furthermore, in some situations, they are willing to share their information in order to gain some benefits such as free services, although sharing behaviour is against their standard to protect their privacy. Therefore, a privacy

paradox can be released as the difference between attitude and behaviour on privacy: although caring very much about personal information and not trusting the reliability of existing data collecting devices and services, nevertheless, people still continue the actions that may increase the possibility of the leaking of their personal data. Awad and Krishnan (2006) and Xu et al. (2011) try to develop a framework to research the reason behind this phenomenon. Hargittai and Marwick (2016) explain it through focus group research. They conclude the term 'What can I do?', indicate that young people feel that in the digital era, no matter how they are concerned, they do not have the ability to control how their information is circulating, therefore the only thing they can do is just let it go. Barth and de Jong (2017) point out that people would evaluate the privacy risk and anticipated benefit and would trade some personal information that is not too important for them for some advantages. Nevertheless, Kokolakis (2017) thinks there are gaps in current research about privacy paradox and suggests that it should use evidence of actual behaviour rather than self-reported behaviour, which means that observation research method is lacked in previous research.

From the literature organized in this chapter, recent studies show that scholars are focusing more on "Data" and "Digital" when it comes to talking about "Privacy", and it shapes how "Privacy" is discussed nowadays.

2.2 Social Media and Digital Privacy

2.2.1 Data and Social Media

'Social media is a virtual community and online platform that lets users create, share, exchange ideas, opinions, and experiences...The biggest difference between social media and general mass media is that users have more abilities and rights to choose and edit its contents' (Mayfield, 2011). From this, social media can be considered as the epitome of Web 2.0. Then, look at the recent statistics (Salim, 2019), globally, people spend most of their time on social media when using the Internet.

Therefore, it can be surmised that most Internet data that input by humans are stored on social media. The richness of data on social media attracts business (Malthouse et al., 2013) and government (Bertot, Jaeger and Hansen, 2012) to collect and analyse. Then the same as the situation of the Internet itself, people start questioning about privacy protection on social media (Acquisti, Brandimarte and Loewenstein, 2015).

2.2.2 Research about Privacy on Social Media

Krasnova et al. (2010) explore the motivation of people to share their private information on social media, and they find that the main reason behind it is because people want to enjoy the

social media platform more easily. For example, like Facebook, the notion of it is connecting with other people, and in order to do that, some personal information must be shown on the profile so that people can find someone specifically or be found. Therefore, users choose to provide their details in order to engage the platform. Bertot, Jaeger and Hansen (2012) mention government usage on social media. They think that the privacy issue needs to be concerned obviously because when people sharing something on social media, they do not anticipate that their sharing will be shared, and it raises the potential ethical problem that does the government have the right uses social media data without user's consent? However, Bertot, Jaeger and Hansen (2012) still consider social media technologies nowadays as an opportunity because, for example, for police, they can use this technology to trace someone and fight crime more easily. Pensa, Di Blasi and Bioglio (2019) develop a model to score the privacy risk of a social media platform, which can be used to help the existing platforms to improve their privacy policies and privacy settings. Degirmenci (2020) focus on mobile devices, and the reason it is related to social media so much is that user's usage habits show that social media apps occupy a big proportion when using mobile devices. His study suggests that asking permission to app users can help to reduce their privacy anxiety, for example, social media apps should as if they can access users' other functions of their smartphone such as camera or location services.

Some research discusses the influence of age and gender on the attitudes on social media privacy. Fogel and Nehmad (2009) research on the gender difference within college students, and the result shows that men are more willing to take the privacy risk on social media than women, for example, men are more likely to put their telephone numbers on their Facebook profile. This reflects Krasnova et al. (2010)'s research because compared to women, the reason for men to take the risks is to enjoy the social media platform. Lin and Wang (2020) explore more details in gender's difference. Their results support Fogel and Nehmad (2009)'s study that women are more concerned about privacy on social media, however, they separate the will of privacy risks taking and information sharing, and indicate that although despite the privacy concerns, there are other factors such as social presence and social ties that influence women's social media behaviour, and these factors are actually making women share more private information on social media. Walrave, Vanwesenbeeck and Heirman (2012) focus on the age difference, and their finding shows that teenagers have more positive attitudes on sharing private information within social media, and they also more relaxed in terms of privacy settings, and the reason behind it is because they like to communicate with their friends and classmates on social media, which echoes Krasnova et al. (2010)'s opinion about the enjoyment of social media platforms, and adults prefer direct communications such as face-to-face, email or phone.

Privacy situation on individual social media platform has also been researched, and Facebook is the most-noticed platform. Dwyer, Hiltz and Passerini (2007) and Fogel and Nehmad (2009) both survey the difference of privacy attitude of users on Facebook and Myspace. Their results both show that people trust Facebook more and are more willing to share private information on it. However, Fogel and Nehmad (2009) indicate the potential reason behind it is because Facebook was restricted to students until 2006, people may feel that it is safer to know the audience they share their information with, and this is going to change because Facebook has taken down this restriction. Christofides, Muise and Desmarais, (2009)'s research finds that the extent of young people's privacy concerns on Facebook and their privacy protecting behaviour do not correlate negatively, which means that despite the privacy concerns, young people are still sharing things such as party photos or birthday dates on Facebook. It can be related to Krasnova et al. (2010)'s opinion that sharing information on social media can let people have more fun on it. However, Boyd and Hargittai (2010)'s survey shows the trend that young people are actually gradually restricting their privacy settings on Facebook. Ayaburi and Treku (2020) explore people's reaction of privacy leaking events of Facebook, and the result shows that these leaking events will reduce people's trust of social media platforms, and affect their decision making of information sharing. Chen and Cheung (2018)'s research is one of the few which studies Chinese social media, and it focuses on WeChat. They indicate that WeChat as a social media platform blur the boundary between private and public because it is not only used for private communication but also for learning and working, and for this, they accuse that WeChat does not protect their user's information privacy enough. However, the reason for the lack of privacy protection on WeChat may relate to Chinese official policy that social media platforms are required to share their user's information to the government, and this will be discussed in the next chapter.

In scholars' opinion, the phenomenon of privacy paradox is also shown on social media. Barnes (2006) first identifies this phenomenon. She points out the paradox between privacy concerns and teenagers' information-sharing behaviour on social media and suggests solving this problem from the educational and legal aspects. However, she indicates that joining a social media platform means to give up some privacy, and questions that if privacy is still existing in the era of social media, which reflects Ohm (2010)'s opinion that anonymity is no use in the information era. The result of Christofides, Muise and Desmarais (2009)'s study is a disclose of privacy paradox because it shows that privacy risks do not always affect people's privacy-protective behaviour on social media. Young and Quan-Haase (2013) accuse social media platforms themselves as the reason causes privacy paradox. They find that users believe that social media can protect their personal data and provide enough privacy settings, therefore, despite the privacy concerns, they are still willing to share their information on the

platforms. Hence, Young and Quan-Haase (2013) conclude that people are not aware enough about the potential risk of data collecting organisations such as social media. Wu (2019) explores this issue in a sociological aspect and conclude that it is about digital identity. People will share the information in order to fulfil the image they want to be seen online, therefore; it increases privacy disclosure even with the awareness of privacy risks. And this supports the notion of privacy, which was organized in the previous chapter, that it is about the control of personal information.

2.3 The Great Firewall

2.3.1 What Is It?

Although China always claims itself has an open society, in fact, China is afraid of the freedom of the exchange of information with the outside world (Smith, 2002). In order to avoid the riots caused by the incoming thoughts and maintain their one-party system, as a solution, “The Great Firewall” has been built (Mulvenon and Chase, 2006). There are mainly two functions that the Great Firewall provides. First, it allows the China government to Internet activities in their country more easily. When entering or leaving China’s Internet, there is a barrier set by the government that must have been through. By monitoring the barrier, the government could deny information with specific keywords to pass through the barrier or block user’s access to certain IPs that are on their blacklist (Einhorn and Elgin, 2006). In addition, the Chinese government also hires over 30,000 employees surfing the Internet manually to finish this task (Einhorn and Elgin, 2006). Second, it blocks Chinese Internet users to enter popular western social media platforms and only allow them to use local social media platforms that are permitted by the Chinese government (Ge and Gretzel, 2017). And this relates to the first function as a monitor way because the Chinese government is not able the control social media platforms that are based in other countries. In order to prevent sensitive information by entering through an external and uncontrollable platform, they simply allow users to use only the platforms that can be monitored.

As a result, a different social media world is isolated within the Firewall, and in this world, users have different Internet usage habits and different social media behaviour (Fong, 2009).

2.4 Privacy Policies and Settings on Social Media

In this chapter, privacy policies and privacy settings within five different social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, WeChat, Weibo) are analysed and compared. There are two goals for the analysis, first is to explore what promises these platforms make to protect users’ data information, and find out if these platforms are hiding something in their privacy policies

that actually allow them to give users' information to third party organisations; second is to see generally what kind of privacy settings these platforms provide.

2.4.1 Platform Chosen

From recent statistics (Chaffey, 2019), it can be seen that for people outside the great firewall, top three most used social media platforms are Facebook, Instagram and Twitter; for people inside the great firewall, top two most used platforms are WeChat and Weibo, and the usage of the third platform is too low compared to top two so it is excluded. Therefore, these five platforms are used for this chapter.

2.4.2 Privacy Policies

All these platforms claim that they are protecting users' data and say that the data is mainly used to help improve their platform. They indicate that users' data would only be shared to third-party organisations when the user allows it, for example, you can sign up for some websites with social media accounts, and if you do that, your account information would be shared with them.

Facebook, Instagram and Twitter say that in some circumstances, users' data would be shared with others without their permission. First is that it is required by law, if the administration appropriately follows the legal process to ask for some data, platforms may have no choice. Second, they mention about third-party partners such as advertisers. They use the excuse that because they are providing their platforms for free to everyone, in order to maintain operating, they must cooperate with other organisations, and this may cause the exchange of users' data. Who are these cooperative partners are not indicated clearly in their policy?

WeChat and Weibo both indication another situation about data sharing: when it comes to national safety. They must share users' information by the government require even if the government doesn't follow the legal process. These two platforms also point out that they require user's specific information such as real name, national ID number and occupation. This can be related to the Real Name Policy of the Chinese government, so the government can control their people more easily.

To sum up, all these platforms are potentially sharing users' data with third-party organisations without users' knowing. Furthermore, Chinese social media platforms are more controlled by the government, are sharing users' data with the government is mandatory.

2.4.3 Privacy Settings

Privacy settings on Facebook, Instagram and Twitter all focus on visible settings, which means the control of who can see users' posts and personal profile. People can decide whether their account is private, or control who can send a friend request. However, when it comes to organisation data collecting, their privacy settings seem to be not enough. Only Facebook and Twitter provide a setting to stop users being tracked by advertisers, but according to their policies, there are other organisations can obtain these data. These platforms do not give their users enough choice to control their data sharing with organisations in privacy settings.

WeChat has a very strict degree of privacy. Only user's contact can see the user's posting, and if I comment on or like other user's post, my contact cannot see it if he is not a contact of the other user. On the contrary, Weibo lacks visible control. Your posts on Weibo are default shown to everyone, and you cannot adjust it. Like western social media, WeChat and Weibo do not provide settings to prevent data collecting by other organisations, moreover, they don't even provide trace prevent function like Facebook or Twitter.

2.5 Emphases of Literature Review

There are several emphasises can be learned from the literature review:

The notion of "Privacy" can be understood. "Privacy" is about people's control of how and what kind of their personal information is shared (Westin, 1968; Allen, 1988). The need for anonymity is an important reason behind privacy (Gavison, 1980), and the degree of intimacy with the information-sharing objects will trigger people's privacy behaviour (Inness, 1996). Later research in the digital era also supports this interpretation of privacy that it is people's decision to choose the way they want to share their data (Nissenbaum, 2009).

There is a paradigm shift in privacy research. Before 2000, scholars' researches about privacy mainly focus on patients' privacy (Shah, 1970; Lewis, 1975) and survey participants' privacy (Ware and Caldwell, 1972; Kelman, 1977). Then with the rise of "Web 2.0" and "Big Data", "Digital" and "Data" shape scholars' research direction nowadays. This can be realised from the research areas about privacy after the 2000s which are organised in chapter 2.1.4.

Anonymity may be impossible in the information era. With the rise of technologies, organisations such as commercial and government can easily access people's data (Boyd and Crawford, 2012), furthermore, we are required to provide our data in order to live in this society (Cullen, 2009). Therefore, some scholars state that anonymity, which is an important connotation of privacy, is dead in the digital age (Haggerty and Ericson, 2000; Prabhakar, Pankanti and Jain, 2003; Ohm, 2010).

Social media should be an important research field in digital privacy. From statistics (Salim, 2019), most human activities online are on social media, therefore, most of the data is stored on it. For such a large database, privacy issues cannot be ignored.

The emergence of privacy paradox. Privacy paradox is a phenomenon that the relationship between the extent of people's privacy concern and action of privacy protection does not show a positive correlation, and it emerges in the digital age (Norberg, Horne and Horne, 2007; Barth and de Jong, 2017; Gerber, Gerber and Volkamer, 2018). The reason behind this phenomenon on social media may be is because of people's need to fully engage in it. (Krasnova et al., 2010)

There is a different social media world. China government builds "The Great Firewall" to monitoring the internet behaviour of their people (Mulvenon and Chase, 2006), hence, only social media platforms that are approved can exist inside the firewall (Ge and Gretzel, 2017). From this, a different social media world with over 13 billion users is created (Fong, 2009).

There are potential privacy risks in current privacy policies and settings in social media. In some situations, social media can share their users' data with other organisations, and who are these organisations are not mentioned in their privacy policies very clear. Most of the platforms provide enough privacy settings for users to control the visibility of their social media content, however, they tend not to provide options for users to decide whether their information would be shared with other organisations.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Question

3.1.1 Research Methods in Previous Studies

There have already been lots of studies about people's attitudes and actions on the Internet. Sheehan and Hoy (2000) use a random email qualitative survey to find out what kind of privacy issues may concern online customers. Their proposes are to see if there was a missing point in the regulation about information gathering developed by the FTC (Federal Trade Commission in America) and give Internet merchants a reference to follow. Bellman et al. (2004) explore widely, they do not just focus on internet customers in one area but more international. They recruit participants via email from 38 countries, ask them to do a survey to see the difference of privacy concerns between different cultures, and the influence of privacy regulation in different countries. Ha and Stoel (2009)'s research focusses broadly on online purchasers' behaviour. Although concern for information privacy is only a small part of their study, it still has a contribution that it starts sampling the age group of participants and only researching college students, which are the major target audience for online marketers based on their research. Krumm (2009)'s study interestingly focuses on an area of Internet privacy: location privacy. Nevertheless, it only researches on technological aspects such as algorithm and data gathering techniques and excludes the non-technological aspects.

There have also been several studies narrow down the research field to social media. Acquisti and Gross (2006), Tufekci (2008) and Boyd and Hargittai (2010)'s papers all select Facebook as the social media platform to research about privacy. Acquisti and Gross (2006) and Tufekci (2008) both explore the difference of the extent of Internet privacy concern between users and non-users of social media by doing a survey on university students; Tufekci (2008) only indicates privacy concern is a significant difference between Facebook users and non-users, and Acquisti and Gross (2006) discuss more about the different behaviours such as control of personal information on the Internet. Boyd and Hargittai (2010) also use qualitative survey method and chose university students as participants, but on the contrary, their research mainly focusses on members of the platform to see their awareness and actions of privacy settings. Fogel and Nehmad (2009)'s privacy study looks up more broadly on social media platforms not just Facebook but also Myspace and Friendster. However, the chosen platforms can be considered outdated at this moment.

3.1.2 *Identifying the Gaps*

There are two gaps that can be identified in these researches. First, most of them only focused on e-commerce area. However, as mentioned in the literature review chapter, internet users engage social media the most when using the Internet, and social media obtains a lot of user's data on the Internet. It may lose the opportunity to fully understand people's behaviour about privacy if research only includes online purchasing field. Second, when they research on social media, they usually only limit to one or several social media platforms, and mainly on Facebook. This creates bias because of the Great Firewall's affection, 13 billion people live behind the Firewall cannot use western social media. As a result, it produces a completely different usage habit of social media compared to the western world. To understand "Privacy" on social media more universally, the variable of the Great Firewall needs to be considered.

3.1.3 *Aim of this Dissertation*

To fill the gaps in previous research, there are two aims of this dissertation. First is to explore what are people's attitudes and actions on overall social media, instead of just looking at a specific platform like previous research did. Therefore, participants will be focused on existing social media users and not including non-members as previous research, and social media platforms will not be only limited to a specific one. Second is to see if the Great Firewall has an affection. As mentioned previously, current studies miss the aspect of views other than in the western world. Due to China's Great Firewall, the social media world is divided into two. If the on Chinese's privacy behaviour on social media is not too different from Chinese, then current studies may be representative enough; if the situation is on the contrary, then a new research aspect of privacy may be able to identify and explore.

To sum up, here are the research questions for this dissertation:

1. What are people's attitudes and actions of privacy on social media?
2. Is there any difference of the attitudes and actions of privacy between non-Chinese (outside the Great Firewall) and Chinese (inside the Great Firewall) social media users?

3.2 Research Method

3.2.1 *Research Method Choosing: Face-to-face Semi-structured Interview*

There are mainly two directions to do social research: quantitative and qualitative research methods (Bryman, 1988; Burns, 2000; Creswell, 2009; Blaxter, 2010). Reliability and Validity play an important part in quantitative research (Maxwell, 1992; Golafshani, 2003). For social research in a quantitative way, it means that the research materials such as questionnaire

need to be examined to fulfil the standard in reliability and validity before it is really applied (Winter, 2000; Grinnell and Unrau, 2005). There have been some examined quantitative research materials about privacy concern in previous studies, however, the area of this dissertation is focused on social media and there have not been a material that matches the topic, so a new one must be created if a quantitative method was chosen. It is possible to develop a questionnaire for this research, nevertheless, because of the limitation of resources and ability, the new-developed questionnaire may not be examined for reliability and validity before it is applied, which can create potential bias that make its result not representative enough. Also, creating a verified questionnaire is not the aim of this dissertation and should not be put too much effort on it. Therefore, quantitative research method may not be suitable for this research.

Grounded theory in qualitative research method seems to be an ideal method for this research. Grounded theory is a method that when researchers begin conducting research, they do not have a hypothesis. Instead, they discover a concept through the process of collecting, observing and analysing data, then generalise it to abstract theory. In other words, this method develops a theory through practical experience instead of coming up with a theory to explain a phenomenon (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Charmaz, 2006). Considering the aim of this dissertation, it is to discover people's attitudes and actions of privacy on social media not to use a theory to explain people's behaviour of privacy on social media, therefore, the proper way to research it is by understanding current user behaviour and organising it to different factors. To sum up, qualitative grounded theory is a method that suits this research.

An interview is a common way to do qualitative grounded theory research (Charmaz, 2001; Duffy, Ferguson and Watson, 2004) There are mainly three kinds of interviews: Structured, Semi-structured and Unstructured (Liamputtong and Ezzy, 2005; Adams and Cox, 2008; Flick, 2009). A structured interview means that the interview is processed by a strictly structured schedule and questions. It makes the interviewer easier to do the interview and analyse the results, however, it does not provide the flexibility to dig interviewee's thoughts deeper which may cause the missing opportunity to fully explore the research subject. On the contrary, there are no scheduled questions in an unstructured interview. Instead, the interviewer just has several topics and let the conversation flow. In this way, the interviewee's mind can be fully explored, and in-depth information can be provided. Nevertheless, it lacks efficiency and makes the results difficult to be analysed. A semi-structured interview balances the structured and unstructured. There are some setting questions in it, and it also lets the interviewer to extend the questions to follow up the interviewee's mind when interesting thoughts come out. The compromise makes the semi-structured interview an effective interview method, therefore, it is chosen for this research.

To sum up, a face-to-face semi-structured interview is an ideal method, and it is used in this research.

3.2.2 Develop Interview Questionnaire

Buchanan et al. (2007) develop a set of questions to research people's actions and attitudes on privacy when using the Internet. However, there are two gaps in Buchanan et al.'s work that make it not suitable for this research. First is that it mainly focused on the whole Internet usage instead of just social media. Therefore, some questions need to be adjusted, and some which are not relevant to social media need to be excluded. Second, it is a 2007 study, and it was more than ten years ago when these questions were developed. Considering the time period when it was developed, it missed some important latest technologies that may affect people's behaviour on digital privacy. For example, questions about location service are not included in this work. In order to fix this problem, another more recent study (Black, Setterfield and Warren, 2018) is brought in to help adjust the interview questions. Although the study is only a literature review of internet privacy research, however, its review structure considers the development of nowadays technologies that can be helpful to solve the outdated problem in Buchanan et al. (2007)'s research.

3.2.3 Participants Sampling and Approaching

The age of participants is carefully chosen. According to a recent statistic about demographics on social media (Mander and Kavanagh, 2019), people in the age group 16 to 34 engage in social media the most (over 50%). Therefore, excluding the ages that may cause ethical problems, the ideal age group of participants should be 18 to 34.

According to recent statistics (Mantle, 2019), around 80% of students in higher education institutions are under 29, which fits our required participant's age group. Therefore, a university is a suitable place to take place this research.

Another variable of participant's demographic that needs to be manipulated is nationality. In order to find out if the Great Firewall affects people's attitudes and actions of privacy, participants' nationality is carefully chosen. Ideally, there should be half of the participants with Chinese nationality and half of the participants with non-Chinese nationality. In this way, it may be able to equally compare the results.

3.2.4 Results of Participants

Here are the final participants of this research: Participants are students at the University of York, 12 of them were recruited. There are one male and eleven females in participants and

the age ranges from 22 to 31. Half of them are from China, and half of them are not. Convenient sampling was used, and they were randomly recruited and interviewed separately on the University of York campus.

3.2.5 Analysis: Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is used to analyse the result of the interview, and there are ten themes can be identified from the interview:

Privacy Self-evaluation: This part focuses on to what extent participants think of themselves to be protective of privacy on social media and explores the reasons why they think so.

Social Media Usage: This part identifies what kind of social media platforms participants use the most, and checks if the reasons they choose to join a social media platform relate to privacy.

Password: This part tries to find out how participants manage their password on social media, checks if they change it frequently and how strong their password they think.

Personal Information: This part is about how participants manage their personal information on their profiles on social media, to see what kind of information they are willing to share publicly.

Private Policy: This part checks if participants read terms and privacy policy before joining a social media platform, asks the reasons why or why nor read it.

Privacy Settings: This part is about if participants are aware of the privacy settings on social media, and if they do what they function do they adjust.

Location and Wi-Fi: This part explores whether participants value their location as important information and think it needs to be protected. Also, participants' attitude accessing social media accounts when using Wi-Fi is included in this part.

Device and Platform Difference: This part tries to find out participants' thoughts that if they think there is a difference in privacy level between devices, brands of devices and social media platforms.

Activities Protection: This part focuses on how the participants do with their activities such as research history on social media, to see how they feel about this information.

Anticipated Data Usage: This part identifies participants' anticipation of how their data on social media would be used, and what kind of third-party organisations they think is collecting and obtaining their data.

4 Results

4.1 Privacy Self-evaluation

All the participants are aware of the dangers of the internet, and they think themselves as a protective person about their privacy on social media.

'I think the internet is not a safe place, so when it comes to personal information, I feel like we need to be more careful.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

'I am very serious about the privacy risks on social media... If I can score myself from 1 to 10, 10 means very concerned, I think I will give myself an 8.' - Participant G (Chinese)

However, for Chinese social media users, most of them indicate that although they know about the dangers, they do not know what kind of actions are required for data protection on social media.

'I am aware of privacy issues on social media, I do not post too much personal information on social media, however, I do not have a strategy or specific actions do protect it.' - Participant J (Chinese)

'The thought of the need of protecting privacy on social media has always been in my mind, however, I don't know what kind of action to take.' - Participant K (Chinese)

Several of both Chinese and non-Chinese specifically talk about some topics that they won't reveal on social media, family-related information is one.

'But in certain aspects, I'm concerned. Let's say I will not be open about I will not expose information about my children or other family members, because it's not my right. If the information I am sharing is just about me, it's okay.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

'I post a lot of things about me only on social media... I do not share something such as my address, or anything about my family, their name or their job etc. will not be shown in my posts. I think my friend on social media do not even know if I have a sibling or not.' - Participant G (Chinese)

'I use a lot of social media platforms... but the only thing I won't share is the photo of my family members. I do not want to let other people know too much about my family.' - Participant H (Chinese)

And money-related information is another issue that they tend not to show on social media.

'When it comes to money, I would be very concerned... I won't share anything about like bank account information on social media.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'My social media is connected to my money... because in China we can use a platform like WeChat as a type of payment, so I am very careful not to leak these kinds of information on social media.' - Participant K (Chinese)

They all have some strategies to prevent privacy leak, but there is a difference between non-Chinese and Chinese social media users. For non-Chinese users, they tend to focus on privacy settings and use them as a privacy defence.

'I make sure that for example, no one that I don't accept to be friends from some platforms like Facebook can really search my profile, see my posts or anything that I do. Like on Instagram, I have a private account... So, I have all the privacy settings on, and for example, like on Facebook, I do not open the last scene function, it's like showing when you go online. Therefore, people even for my friend accounts cannot really see when I'm online... I think I do put a lot of effort to block everyone who is not my friend in real life on social media.' - Participant B (Non-Chinese)

For Chinese social media users, they tend to limit the content of their posts and consider the characters of each social media platform when sharing something.

'I join different social media platforms for different purposes... some platforms I join is for connecting with my friends, and some are for my personal habits... I will make sure that what I share on each platform fits the purpose I join, and I won't share anything else that is not too relevant.' - Participant G (Chinese)

4.2 Social Media Usage

For social media platform usage, top three platforms for non-Chinese participants are Facebook (6 of them), Instagram (5 of them), and Twitter (3 of them); top two platforms for Chinese are WeChat and Weibo, all of them are using these two platforms. The third most used platform is Zhihu, but only two of them are using it.

For non-Chinese, they tend to only use famous social media platforms such as Facebook. The friend is an important factor for them to choose a social media platform or not, if most of their friends are on a platform, they would probably join it.

'I would rather join a social media platform with a big name, such as Facebook or Instagram, not a small one, even if it seems to be interested. I feel like platforms with a bigger reputation maybe can provide a more secure environment from users and have more ability to protect our data privacy... Maybe I would join a platform if most of my friends are on it, but if it is only a few, even if it is my close friend, I would rather not join the platform.' - Participant B (Non-Chinese)

'Perhaps I would join an infamous social media, but the chance is small. I mean, usually, what dictates for me is if my friends are on that, if my friends are on there, I want to be able to contact them. And that's the easiest way for them. For me to do that, then I might get that agenda I would trust. If my friends have it, then it's probably safe... If my best friend recommends a smaller social media to me, I will probably do some research about it, but if it was a good number of friends, then I might take it more seriously.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

For Chinese, they are more open-minded on the platform chosen. They would join a platform which is interested in them, even if it is a small, infamous one. From this, Chinese social media world provides more platform options, and the purpose of each platform is more specific. This probably explains the reason for the dramatic drop of user number other than WeChat and Weibo in statistics because other than the top two platforms they would join whatever platforms they want and tend not to consider how many people are using it.

'I love Chinese drama; therefore, I have joined some social media platforms that focus on such as news of Chinese drama or gossip about Chinese actors.' - Participant G (Chinese)

'I would probably join some social media platforms that interest me. For example, I am interested in poetry, and recently I joined a platform for people to share their poetry work and discuss their favourite poets.' - Participant H (Chinese)

'I am currently on some social media platforms about comics and animations. We will talk about the latest episodes of some serials, and sometimes share some resources that may not be legal. Japanese manga is great!!' - Participant I (Chinese)

Some Chinese participants point out that sometimes it is purposeful for them to join a social media platform, maybe for some benefits, maybe for chasing a file.

'Based on my need (to join a smaller social media platform). Sometimes I want to buy something, but the seller is only on a specific social media platform than I would join it. But only for purchasing the product.' - Participant J (Chinese)

'If I want to download something, sometimes the file is on a small social media platform, and I have to sign up to get the file then I would join the platform... but I won't be too serious about the platform and probably won't keep using it in the future...It's purposeful.' - Participant K (Chinese)

4.3 Password

Most of the participants are using different but similar passwords among different social media platforms. The reason behind it is because they have difficulty to remember too many passwords. They tend to be aware of using similar passwords may increase privacy risks, however, they still choose the convenience.

'I tend to have a couple of passwords that I flip between for different things. But I don't know, I'm not very good at learning passwords are memorising them. So, I have like three or four that I can flip between... if someone learns one of those passwords, they can figure out practice multiple things. That's more dangerous than having unique ones, but I don't know if anyone really cares that much.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'I used to use very different passwords among different social media platforms, however, it caused me some problems that I forgot what password on each platform very often. Therefore, now I use similar passwords in order to memorise it more easily.' - Participant E (Non-Chinese)

Most of the participants consider their passwords are safe. They all use a combination of numbers, letters and special characters.

'I think the strength of my passwords is fine. I always follow the suggestion from the platform, combine numbers, letters (capital and non-capital) and special characters to create my passwords. Furthermore, I always turn on the second level of authentication function on social media, so I think I do not need to create a very complicated one.' - Participant F (Non-Chinese)

'I think my passwords are in medium strength, I use both numbers and letters... I think my passwords are probably not too safe but okay.' - Participant I (Chinese)

They tend to not change their passwords. One reason is that they couldn't remember the change all the time and think they may be confused with the old and new one. The second reason is that they do not think the password is a useful tool to prevent data leaking. If someone wants to hack their accounts, they don't think a strong password would stop it.

'Maybe it would make me safer (to change my passwords more frequently). I used to do that as well. And then I started like, confusing my old password to the new one. It was kind of messy.' - Participant A (Non-Chinese)

'I don't think changing password could make your accounts safer, because I feel like if someone is trying to break into it, then they're going to just break into whatever the password is... if someone really wants to hack, you know, hacking is not going to matter.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'I don't change my passwords very often...but sometimes some social media platforms would ask you to change it, therefore, I have three or four similar combinations to handle this situation... I know there might be some privacy risks, but now I feel like the convenience is more important because I believe if a hack wants to access my account a password will not stop him.' - Participant L (Chinese)

Most of them are using the "Remember me" function because they don't want to type their password repeatedly. However, they only allow this function on trusted devices.

'I use remember me function, but only with normal social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter. I don't allow remember function on my email because I feel like sometimes there is important information in it like my bank account or something.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

'I'm lazy, okay. I don't really want to have to keep typing it, but only if it's a device that I own if it on my phone or my laptop I will use remember me, but if it's on a public computer then I won't.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'I always use remember me function on my devices. In fact, I don't even know my password to access my Weibo account because the computer helps me remember it.' - Participant J (Chinese)

4.4 Personal Information

Participants tend to show their personal information on their social media profile to their friends, they would adjust privacy settings to make sure only people they know can see this information.

'My policy with Facebook is, I don't have I have a few things public as possible and try to keep everything friends only. And sometimes, things I will just keep only to me. That's only if it's something for me, and I don't want people to know about it.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'Actually, I hide my information on purpose. I do really like people to find me on social media. I only show my information to my friends, my REAL friends in REAL life... Well to my friends, I feel confident to share my birthday, my contact information etc. because I know who they are.' - Participant G (Chinese)

Only providing general and not too specific details is a strategy for them to protect information.

'If I want to show something on social media, I would put something not too detail. For example, I show where I live now on Facebook, but it is not a very specific place, it is just something broadly like UK or England.' - Participant E (Non-Chinese)

'I show my birthday on my social media profile because I want people to know it and wish me happy birthday when the date comes ha-ha. However, I don't show what year it is because it's too detail.' - Participant I (Chinese)

For non-Chinese, some of the information would be provided more specific for some purpose. For example, a detailed education for job hunting, or specific location for networking.

'I will show my education information on social media because I feel like showing this information can attract some job opportunities, I think.' - Participant A (Non-Chinese)

'I put my education information publicly because I would like others to find me on social media more easily because there are other people have the same name and if I put my education my friend can verify the account is really me...I also showed my location information like where I live now because I want people to know where I live so it can help me to get a job.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

For Chinese, their strategy is to provide false information or create fake accounts. This can be related to the diversity of Chinese social media platforms that they use fake information to join a smaller platform.

'I do provide false information on some social media platforms. Like when a platform interests me and I want to join, however, it is a small one and maybe not that secure then I would just put fake information. Furthermore, I won't use these

small platforms to connect with my real friends, therefore I don't need to provide my real information to let them find me.' - Participant H (Chinese)

'I have several fake accounts. I use them to share something I do not want my friends to know.' - Participant K (Chinese)

4.5 Private Policy

The length of terms and conditions is the reason why all participants don't read it.

'It's too long.' - All participants

'I don't think there are very many people in the world who do read them.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

They will still agree with the terms and conditions because the need for using the platform is more important. Also, some of the participants indicate that they feel that all platforms are providing similar privacy policies, so you just need to read one.

'I don't read the terms and conditions before joining a social media platform... but I will still agree to join the platform. If I decide to join a platform, I would probably agree with everything they ask for.' - Participant F (Non-Chinese)

'If you do not agree, then you cannot sign up to the platform. It is like a forced choice and you have to agree to everything no matter what if you still want to use the platform.' - Participant H (Chinese)

'I tend to broadly scan these terms and conditions, but do not read it carefully... I feel like this information is all some on every social media, and you cannot disagree with it because if you do that then you can't join the platform and then how do you communicate with your friends? How do you know their recent status?' - Participant J (Chinese)

In most of the participants' minds, they do not like to accept these terms and conditions, and they all think about that social media platforms may hide something potentially violate their privacy in their terms and conditions, and platforms know that users are not going to read but just allow it. However, some of the participants consider it is the users' responsibility to be more careful about what we are accepting.

'I should probably one day sit down to carefully read these terms and conditions... I feel like it would probably tell me a lot about what they use.' - Participant B (Non-Chinese)

'It's our fault to not read it because they already tell you what they are going to do with our data... it's up to you as a user to provide your data or not, and if you don't read it, and then they use it, it's the users' false.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

'I believe these platforms almost certainly do put something in their terms and make us share our data with others, and they know we won't read it and just agree with it no matter what... You know, the difference between me being able to contact my friends or not, then it's just a price to pay.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

Some of the participants choose not to share something too private on social media because of the concern of what they have accepted.

'That is why choose not to, to share, like the stuff I don't want them to. So, whatever I share on social media, it's because I really don't care.' - Participant A (Non-Chinese)

'So, I don't share information that is too private to me on social media.' - Participant E (Non-Chinese)

'The information I share on social media is not important to me, therefore, if the platform wants to share it, it's fine.' - Participant J (Chinese)

4.6 Privacy Settings

Participants have a strong desire to adjust privacy settings, and they would not leave it default. Moreover, some of them would check it constantly to make sure their sharing on social media is only visible to the audience they want.

'I constantly review these (Privacy settings). Because I don't like to share everything with everyone. Somethings I just share with my closest friends.' - Participant A (Non-Chinese)

'I attempted that (Privacy settings) probably more than most people I would imagine. I'm quite rigorous about my privacy... make sure to keep a close eye on what's visible and what's not.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'I will make sure that my account, for example, my Instagram account, to be private so that only people I am allowed can see my posts... I also constantly adjust the timeline on my Facebook so that my new friends cannot see my old photos.' - Participant F (Non-Chinese)

'Every time I joined a social media platform, I would immediately go to setting section and change privacy settings... For example, on WeChat, I change that my friends cannot see my post which was six months before. Also, I limited the people who can give me a comment.' - Participant H (Chinese)

'Sometimes social media platforms require your true information to sign up like your birthday, and this kind of information would automatically be shown on your profile. I would change the setting to hide this information or only show them to my friends.' - Participant K (Chinese)

Because of the characters of Chinese social media platforms, Chinese participants have different privacy settings behaviour. Chinese social media platforms give their users' less power to adjust privacy settings, therefore, Chinese users tend not to actively change the settings. Like WeChat, it defaults let only user's contact see the post, and Weibo, it does not allow users to set their posts private.

'Do I need to change privacy settings? I mean on WeChat, everyone who is not my contact cannot see my posts and my comments, I think that is good enough for me. And Weibo, I don't think there are privacy settings, so I just post stuff that is not important to be there.' - Participant I (Chinese)

'I don't change privacy settings because I am lazy... I am not very good at using digital gadgets, so I don't really understand how to change and what to change. Also, I use WeChat the most and I feel like it's default privacy settings is enough.' - Participant J (Chinese)

4.7 Location and Wi-Fi

Most of the participants have used location service in social media before. They would check-in their location when they go somewhere special.

'I use the check-in function several times... If I go somewhere that is special or I know that I would go there once in my entire life, then I would probably show my location in my post.' - Participant E (Non-Chinese)

'Most of the time I open location service on social media is because I am travelling, and I want to share some pictures I shoot there.' - Participant J (Chinese)

They are aware of the privacy risks when using location services, therefore, they have a strategy to protect it: when they check-in on social media, they tend to show a board location

instead of a specific one, like in the UK. Also, they make sure that the location services would be opened only when they need it.

'I am fine sharing my location as long as it's not too specific... and I don't keep opening location service while using social media, I just open it when I need to post something with my location.' - Participant F (Non-Chinese)

'I always check my setting that the location service would only open when I am using social media and do not allow it after I log out... I have some strategies when sharing my location, first, for example, I make sure it only shows a broad location such as a city or a country, second, I don't share my location immediately, I would post it when I am not there already.' - Participant H (Chinese)

They would access their social media accounts when using public Wi-Fi, because of the convenience. But they tend to choose the Wi-Fi that is provided by a trusted institution, which may reduce the privacy risks.

'I do think about it when I'm like on public Wi-Fi is like if it's safe or not. I wouldn't obviously like us like random Wi-Fi on the street. Oh, I probably if I am in like coffee, like Costco, like Starbucks. But I wouldn't just connect like a random one.' - Participant B (Non-Chinese)

'If I need to use it (Public Wi-Fi), I mean, I'd like to think that certain places are safer than others, like library Wi-Fi, safe; shops Wi-Fi, less.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'I will choose Wi-Fi, for example, I will look at the institution which provides this Wi-Fi if I can trust the institution than I would probably use the Wi-Fi.' - Participant G (Chinese)

4.8 Device and Platform Difference

All participants use their smartphones to access their social media accounts. They don't think there is a difference in privacy risks between a smartphone and a PC. They feel like the internet connection and the app itself are more related to privacy risks.

'I don't think that's going to make a difference. But maybe the network provider might make a difference. So, you know, like, O2 versus EE, because they give you your mobile data, that they might perhaps be able to exploit that.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'Most of the time I just use the app version of social media... I think the Wi-Fi connection or social media platforms itself would affect the privacy risk, but not the device. - Participant I (Chinese)

Some of the participants believe that iPhone is safer than other brands when using social media.

'Maybe it's safer to use an Apple phone... I feel like the operating system, like iOS is safer than Android or others.' - Participant A (Non-Chinese)

'I always use an iPhone... Its operating system is simpler, and you change too much on it, so I think it's safer.' - Participant K (Chinese)

4.9 Activities Protection

Non-Chinese participants tend to clear their search history on social media, they believe that this is important information.

'I clean my search often because I don't want to be traced. It's not like I have something bad on it, just, you know, I don't like the feeling that someone can see it.' - Participant B (Non-Chinese)

'I think these are important information for me, so I always try to clean it as often as possible... But I feel like the platform still keep it anyway no matter we clear it or not.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

Chinese participants clear their search history too, but with a different reason. Most of them only clear it when it occupied too many storages of their phone.

'Sometimes it (search history) seems to occupy too much space on my phone, so I will clean it regularly.' - Participant H (Chinese)

'I will clear my search history when the storage of my phone is not enough... Yeah not being traced is one of the reasons too but mainly it's about storage.' - Participant I (Chinese)

Some of the Chinese participants even like to leave it, because they think it can be beneficial for them, like timesaving on typing.

'I will keep my search history because I feel like social media platform would personalise advertisements to me based on it and my kind of like that. Also, it saves

time if you search something more often, it can autotype for you.' - Participant J (Chinese)

'I leave my search history because it can help me remember what I have searched before, and I don't have to type it again if I want to search something the same. It's convenient!' - Participant K (Chinese)

4.10 Anticipated Data Usage

Participants do not believe that social media platforms are protecting their data. Moreover, some of them believe that platforms have no responsibility.

'I do think social media is sharing or applying our data. I mean, legally they may have to protect our data, but we users have agreed with the terms and conditions which means we may have already agreed with the data sharing. That's why I said before that we should sit down one day and read these terms carefully.' - Participant B (Non-Chinese)

'Of course, I think that social media is not protecting our data... I mean, we are the one who is using it and willingly to input our information, I don't think it is platforms' responsibility. I think we are the one should be responsible for our data, and we always have the choice to not use social media.' - Participant G (Chinese)

How they find out that social media may share their data with other organisation is that when they search for something online, there would always be advertisements about it pop on their social media page.

'One day I searched for a flight online, then when I opened social media, I found that there are some discount ads about flight tickets, and the destination is exactly what I searched before. Is that a coincidence? I really don't think so.' - Participant H (Chinese)

'Sometimes I searched something and then I opened social media on the same day I found that there are ads that are like what I searched earlier... I used to think it is annoying but now I just feel like oh it's kind of convenient to find cheaper products.' - Participant K (Chinese)

Some Chinese participants are even willing to exchange their information for some commercial benefits.

'I have joined some marketing campaigns on social media that required me to post something publicly and share my location... I don't think this is harmful to my data because the advertisers just want to increase the level of discussion of their goods.'
- Participant I (Chinese)

'I have post public posts several times for a discount, but only for a really big discount or my favourite bands.' - Participant J (Chinese)

Some of the participants consider that their data is valuable and profitable, therefore it is easy to understand why social media platforms are selling their data.

'It's (users' data) very valuable. It's very useful for the government, for a private company, for everything. This information can be used to manage the population or run a business. So, saying that social media will be protective to your data it's so naive.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

'Profit is what social media is thinking about.' - Participant E (Non-Chinese)

'Information is very valuable nowadays, I think... If this platform doesn't sell it, there would still be others sell it.' - Participant I (Chinese)

The way participants deal with this issue is to just share information that is not too important to them, and for some participants, they eventually stop posting on social media and just browsing.

'I don't necessarily see how harmful my data is, to me when, you know, millions of people stage up are accessible. And if they're just using me to look at statistics, or you know, what's trending, I don't see the harm... if they are looking specifically at my profile to learn things about me, then I might be a bit concerned. If I'm just a statistic, I don't mind.' - Participant D (Non-Chinese)

'So not I am reducing the time on social media... I hardly post something now, I just looking at it to see what is happening now in society.' - Participant E (Non-Chinese)

'I feel like the information I shared on social media is not that important... so they can just take it I don't mind.' - Participant F (Non-Chinese)

Although participants are aware of the commercial usage of their social media data, they do not really think of the data collecting by other organisations like government.

'Government? Maybe they are collecting, I am not sure. Maybe they're interested in I don't know what party I am interested, and my age and you know, like, just to know how to get to me, but maybe they are using it for something else.' - Participant A (Non-Chinese)

'I am not sure the government is collecting my data... I mean, I can see some personalised ads and I know that is definitely based on my data, but I have never seen anything about government pops up on my social media pages.' - Participant I (Chinese)

For some Chinese participants, they feel like they are advantages for the government to collect their social media data.

'You know if the government wants to do some analysis on their population before they need to do a survey or something. Now, they can just look at social media!' - Participant G (Chinese)

Overall, participants feel powerless about the situation that their data is constantly obtained by third-party organisation in this era.

'That's a reality and part of life, I mean, this is a society we are living in now.' - Participant C (Non-Chinese)

'Unless I quit social media, or I can't stop my data being collected.' - Participant k (Chinese)

5 Discussion

5.1 Generating People's Attitudes and Actions of Privacy on Social Media

5.1.1 Attitudes

Overall, people are very concerned about their privacy on social media. They have a very strict standard of who can see their social media contents, and always try to block people they do not know. Scholars' interpretation of privacy can be seen in this that it's about people's control of their information (Westin, 1968; Allen, 1988; Nissenbaum, 2009). Intimacy's effect on privacy (Gavison, 1980) also emerges that people only want someone they know in real life to be friends on social media, and because of the connection in real life (level of intimacy), people can be willing to share their information.

Although people are all aware of the privacy risks on social media, they have pessimistic ideas about preventing risks. They feel like there is no effective way for protection, for example, they think that hackers can access their accounts no matter how complicated their passwords are. Furthermore, they believe that their privacy has gone once they joined a social media platform. They consider their data as a profitable thing for social media, and there is no way platforms won't take advantage of it. From this, it can be realised that people tend to accept the fact from scholars' opinion that anonymity is no use in this era (Haggerty and Ericson, 2000; Prabhakar, Pankanti and Jain, 2003; Ohm, 2010).

5.1.2 Actions

Two main actions that people would take to protect privacy on social media. First is that they constantly adjust privacy settings, to make sure that they have full control of who can see their contents. Second is about the content they share on social media. They try to blur it to not be too detailed, for example, they check-in a broad location not a specific one. Moreover, they try to only provide unimportant information is not harmful to them if it is leaked, and they specifically won't share anything related to their family and money.

5.1.3 Paradox

Privacy paradox emerges in this interview, and it can be seen through their attitudes and behaviours in these three things: password, remember me function and public Wi-Fi. They are all aware of the privacy risks behind them. Convenience is the main reason why people decide to take risks. They use similar passwords to avoid forgetting them; they use remember me function to reduce the number of typing; they access their social media accounts throughout public Wi-Fi because of the convenience.

There can be two directions to explain the paradox. First is about people's powerless attitude of privacy on social media. It can be realised from the interview that people tend to feel that it is hard to prevent their data being leaked if they choose to use social media, and using social media is an important part of this era and they cannot avoid it. From this, because they feel like no matter how protective they are there may be no difference, they just decide to do whatever they want even though it may be against the privacy concern in their mind. The second reason can be related to Krasnova et al. (2010)'s point that people have the need to enjoy the social media platform. From the interview, several participants would take privacy risk in order to achieve some goals. For example, non-Chinese would share their education detail to gain a job, Chinese would join smaller platforms because of interest even the platform seems to be not safe. To sum up, personal purpose can be the reason that makes them take the privacy risks on social media.

A new kind of privacy paradox emerges in this research. Although from the interview people show their privacy concerns and will to adjust privacy settings, however, when it comes to organisations' data collecting behaviour on social media, they do not have a clear idea about it and do not know how to prevent it. They are not aware that organisations other than commercial such as the government are also collecting their data, and they don't read the privacy policy about it before joining a social media. This can be explained that it is because of the social media itself tend not to provide setting functions for users to stop organisations' collecting, and it causes the lack of users' recognition of organisational data gathering behaviour. Furthermore, platforms may intentionally extend the length of their privacy policy to reduce the chance for users to read it, so they can hide some data sharing behaviour in it.

5.2 The Influence of the Great Firewall

In attitudes, Chinese are like non-Chinese. They are both aware of the privacy risks, and they all have negative emotions if their social media contents are shown to someone they don't know. However, they have a more relaxed mindset about organisations' data collecting, they tend to enjoy personalised ads which are based on their activities, and support government's data collecting for the public interest.

The difference in platform usage leads to different actions. From the interview, Chinese adjust less on privacy settings, and this can be related to the platforms they use. Consider the top two platforms they are using: WeChat's privacy features are strict, so it does not require additional settings, and Weibo provides very limited settings, so they don't need to think about it. This leads to the Chinese's lack of adjustment of privacy settings.

6 Conclusion

6.1 What Has Been Done?

The notion of “Privacy” can be understood from the literature review, and scholars are focusing more on “Digital” and “Data” privacy nowadays. However, previous studies either lack the recognition of social media as an important field in privacy nor only focus on several western social media platforms. Therefore, this dissertation aims to answer two questions: 1) What are people’s attitudes and actions of privacy on social media? And 2) Is there any difference of the attitudes and actions of privacy between non-Chinese (outside the Great Firewall) and Chinese (inside the Great Firewall) social media users? A face-face semi-structured interview is used as a method to research the topic.

6.2 Findings

In attitudes, people are very concerned about their privacy on social media and what they really care about is who can see their social media contents. They feel helpless of the privacy risks on social media because they think in modern society, it is necessary to join social media, and if you join social media, there is inevitably a chance for data leaking. There are two actions that they are using to protect their social media privacy, adjusting privacy settings carefully and sharing only limited information. Non-Chinese and Chinese have similar privacy attitudes, but the Chinese have difference protective actions because of the character of the social media platforms they are using.

A new form of privacy paradox is raised from this research. Social media do not provide a way to prevent data collection from the organization causes the issue that despite knowing the privacy risks on social media, people lack awareness and actions about the organization collecting data.

6.3 Limitation and Future Studies

Age and gender are factors that may affect people’s attitudes and actions of privacy (Sheehan, 1999; Garbarino and Strahilevitz, 2004; Livingstone, 2008; Fogel and Nehmad, 2009; Walrave, Vanwesenbeeck and Heirman, 2012; Davis and James, 2013; Crotty et al., 2015; Lin and Wang, 2020) However, in this research, only people in 22 to 31 are studied, and only one of the participants is man, which may not be representative enough. In future studies, age and gender should be more balanced if the direction of research is focusing on general people’s behaviour.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 - Ethics Approval Certificate

2018/19

This certifies that

Y3865633

Has obtained approved research methodology for their postgraduate dissertation following the ethics approval process in the 2018/19 academic year

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Darren Reed".

Dr. Darren Reed
Ethics Committee Chair

Appendix 2 - Interview Consent Form

THE UNIVERSITY *of York*

PROJECT INFORMATION

Hi, I am Ching-Han Kuo, a student at the University of York in the Department of Sociology. I am conducting a research study, which I invite you to take part in.

The purpose of this study is to research people's attitudes and actions of data privacy on social media. You will be interviewed several questions, and it would take approximately 30 minutes. You must be over 18 to take part in this research. The personal information and answers in the interview will be handled and kept anonymous. Results of this study will only be used for research purposes and may be used in publications and presentations. If the results of this study are published or presented, individual names and other personally identifiable information will not be used.

Your participation in this study does not involve any physical or emotional risk to you. You are not likely to have any direct benefit from being in this research study, but we may learn new things that may be used to help other people in the future.

Participation in this study is voluntary. You do not have to answer any questions you do not want to answer, and you may withdraw from this study at any time for any reason. If you decide to withdraw from this study, I will ask you if the information already collected from you can be used.

If you have any further questions and concerns, please contact me via my email: ck960@york.ac.uk. Also, my supervisor Dr David Beer is directing the project and can be contacted via email: david.beer@york.ac.uk

CONSENT FORM

Please tick the boxes below to confirm:

- I confirm that I have read this form and understand the information about this study.
- I have been given the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
- If I have additional questions, I have been told whom to contact.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason. Also, my legal rights will not be affected.
- I give permission for my responses to be saved anonymously.
- I confirm that I am over 18 years old.
- I agree to the researcher to audio record this interview.
- I agree to participate in the research study described.

The interview/interaction will be tape-recorded. The data will be kept strictly confidential and will be available only to me. Excerpts from the data may be made part of the final research report, but under no circumstances will your name or any identifying characteristics be included in the report.

I consent to take part in this research

..... Participant signature

..... Participant name (printed)

..... Date